

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13752812

Influence of Parents' Socioeconomic Status on the Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of parents' socioeconomic status on the career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The research design for the study was the descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised of all Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, which is 5,874. The convenience non-probability sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 588 Senior Secondary School students across 12 secondary schools in Makurdi. A researcher developed questionnaire titled "Students' Career Aspirations Questionnaire (SCAQ)" was administered to gather data on the influence of parents' socioeconomic status on students' career aspirations. The questionnaire was made up of 15 items and followed the four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. Data were analyzed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree. The findings of the study were as follows; parents' income, parents' occupation and parents' educational attainment have significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Keywords: Parents' socioeconomic status, parents' income, parents' occupation, parents' educational attainment, students' career aspiration.

INTRODUCTION

Young people are great dreamers, their life is dominated with dreams and aspirations of what they would do in the future, what they would want to be in the future and even how they would wish to live their lives when they get older. It is not unusual to hear young people say "I will ask my kids what it feels like to be rich man's child." Such statements are expressions of their future desires and aspirations and an acknowledgement of their displeasure with the kind of family they grew up in. A child's social

environment has the potential of influencing their future aspirations about a choice of work or a career path (Buah, Mustapha & Abdullahi, 2020).

A career aspiration is a path that students want to become in future (Laroco, 2022). A career aspiration can be simply said to be a desire for a particular occupation or job to be done in a later time. Career aspiration is an important factor in the process of career development and basically lays the foundation for choice of career and accompanying career decisions. According to Obiyo and Eze (2015) families, parents and guardians play significant role in the career aspirations and career goal development of their children. Literature shows that parents, even though it is not their intention to influence certain vocational choices, are active agents in helping refine their children's choices during their career development process (Nawabi & Javed, 2019). Parental influence on their offspring's career aspirations can be substantial and multifaceted. Basically, these influences exerted on the child are channelled through deliberate and indeliberate behaviours and parents' social standing which is subsumed under socioeconomic status. Socioeconomic status refers to a person's or family's social and economic position in relation to others, often determined by factors like income, education, and occupation.

According to American Psychological Association [APA] (2021), socioeconomic status is the social standing or class of an individual or group. It is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. Examinations of socioeconomic status often reveal inequalities in access to resources, plus issues related to privilege, power and control. Socioeconomic status of parents has been found to be a function of the level of their educational attainment as well as their occupation (Ndubuisi, Anokam, Nwagumma & Unamba, 2018). Jimoh, Adesanya and Shuaib (2018) found in a study that parents' educational level, occupation and income influenced the career aspirations of their offspring.

The occupation of a parent refers to the job or work the parent does to ensure the inflow of income. Saifi and Mehmood (2011) state that, occupational status as one of the components of socioeconomic status comprises income and educational attainment. It corresponds to the educational attainment of an individual through which, obtaining better jobs, exploring and retaining better positions becomes inevitable and thus improvement in the socioeconomic status. A parent's occupation can have a profound influence on a child's career aspirations through various mechanisms. Parents in certain occupations may have access to specialized resources, such as books, tools, or technology related to their field. Children may have the chance to explore and learn from these resources, potentially sparking an interest in the same or related fields. Furthermore, parents often discuss their jobs and career experiences with their children. These conversations can provide insights into the demands, rewards, and challenges of different professions, influencing a child's perceptions and interests.

Parents' income can be said to be salaries, wages, profits, rents, or any other sources of cash inflow or earnings that parents receive at any given time. Another way of looking at income is in the form of worker's compensation, social security, pensions, interests or dividends, royalties, trusts, alimony, or other governmental, public, or family financial assistance (Amandeep, 2016). Parents' income levels can influence the expectations they have for their child's career success. Children from higher income families may experience greater pressure to pursue prestigious or financially rewarding careers (Jamabo, 2014). Higher income families may have the means to send their child to better-funded schools, which can provide a higher quality education. This can lead to exposure to more diverse subjects and potential career paths. Parents with higher incomes often have larger social and professional networks. This can expose a child to a wider array of professions and industries, potentially influencing their career interests. Affluent families can provide access to a wider range of opportunities (Salgotra & Roma, 2018). They may be able to send their child to specialized camps, workshops, or conferences related to certain fields, exposing them to a broader spectrum of career options. It is important to note that while parental income can significantly influence a child's career aspirations, it is not the only factor at play. Personal interests, aptitudes, and passions, as well as societal and cultural influences, also play significant roles in shaping a person's career path.

A person's educational attainment is considered to be the highest level (grade or degree) of education they have completed. Education also plays a role in income (Rani, 2018). Education plays a major role in skill

sets for acquiring jobs as well as specific qualities that stratify people with higher socioeconomic status from lower socioeconomic status (Ranjana, 2014). A parent's educational attainment can significantly influence a child's career aspirations in several ways. Children often look to their parents as role models. If a parent has achieved a high level of education, it can set a precedent and inspire the child to set similar educational and career goals. Parents with higher educational attainment are more likely to be equipped to provide academic support and guidance to their children. They can offer assistance with homework, provide advice on educational pathways, and help navigate the complexities of the education system (Mathatha & Ndlhovu, 2018). Parents with higher educational attainment may have higher expectations for their child's academic performance and educational achievements. This can create a supportive environment for the child to excel academically and set ambitious career goals. Furthermore, well-educated parents may have a wider network of professional connections, which can provide opportunities for mentorship, internships, and exposure to different career options.

While a parent's socioeconomic status can be a significant influence, it is important to note that it is not the only factor at play. Personal interests, aptitudes, and passions, as well as societal and cultural influences, also play significant roles in shaping a person's career path. Ultimately, regardless of their socioeconomic status, parents can support their children in exploring their interests and passions, providing opportunities for learning and growth, and encouraging open communication about career aspirations. This allows children to make informed decisions about their future paths.

Statement of the Problem

The researchers have observed that students from high income families or families with high social standing tend to go into more prestigious careers than their counterparts from low-income families or lower social standing. One of the researcher's recounts dropping out of a better but costlier school to one that was less costly due to an unprecedented life changing experience. This sudden change altered his career aspirations and entire goals as related to choice of career and future occupation. While on teaching practice, the researcher also observed that when students were asked the kind of jobs or occupations, they would like to go into in the future they were usually heard mentioning different occupations. The choice of aspired careers mentioned by students was observed to be influenced by the student's family background and their parents' social status or standing. Students from families where parents were relatively doing well aspired to be like their parents. However, no offspring of farmers aspired to be farmers. This could be because of the socioeconomic atmosphere surrounding the environment the child grew up in and the kind of lifestyle the parents could afford and also provide the child. For the counsellor, these are important factors to be considered in career counselling not just because a student needs to choose a career but also because this decision will affect such a student throughout the lifespan. In the current study the researcher aims to find out how parents' sociodemographic characteristics like income, occupation, education and social capital can influence their child's choice of career. These influences exerted can be latent or manifest but generally affect the kind of career the child would choose to go into. This is because children often look up to their parents as role models and if a child grows up seeing their parents in certain professions, they may be more inclined to consider similar paths. Therefore, it is important to study the influence of a parent's socioeconomic status on their child's career aspirations.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of parents' income on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State?
2. What is the influence of parents' occupation on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State?
3. What is the influence of parents' educational attainment on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Parents’ income has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.
2. Parents’ occupation has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.
3. Parents’ educational attainment has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of all Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State which is 5,874. The convenience non-probability sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 588 Senior Secondary School students across 12 secondary schools in Makurdi. A researcher developed questionnaire titled “Students’ Career Aspirations Questionnaire (SCAQ)” was administered to gather data on the influence of parents’ socioeconomic status on students’ career aspirations. The descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. 2.50 was used as the criterion mean for decision making on the item to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree. The chi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

This section covers a presentation of the results of the study.

Research Question 1

What is the influence of parents’ income on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State?

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Parents’ Income on Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	I have considered pursuing a career primarily for financial stability due to my family's income level.	161	277	80	70	2.90	.937	Accepted
2	There are some careers I like but can't pursue because of financial constraints.	334	184	30	40	3.30	.864	Accepted
3	I feel high pressure to choose a financially lucrative career due to my family's income expectations.	259	249	55	25	3.26	.798	Accepted
4	My family is not very supportive in helping me achieve my career aspirations, considering the financial aspect.	182	301	65	40	3.06	.830	Accepted
5	Individuals from higher-income families have more opportunities in their career paths compared to those from lower-income families.	196	242	100	50	2.99	.919	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation \bar{X}= 3.102 SD= .8696								Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents’ responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.90, 3.30, 3.26, 3.06, and 2.99 with corresponding standard deviations of .937, .864, .798, .830, and .919 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.102 with the cluster standard deviation of .8696 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that parents’ income has influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of parents' occupation on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State?

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Parents' Occupation on Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	The professional field in which my parents work plays a significant role in guiding my career choices.	488	75	25	0	3.79	.503	Accepted
7	I feel that my career options are influenced by the occupational background of my parents.	266	247	50	25	3.28	.793	Accepted
8	The professional experiences of my parents significantly impact the educational opportunities available to me.	210	188	100	90	2.88	1.06	Accepted
9	I have considered pursuing a career similar to that of my parents due to their occupational success.	196	342	40	10	3.23	.645	Accepted
10	I feel a strong influence from my family's professional background to choose a specific career path.	231	237	70	50	3.10	.918	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation \bar{X}= 3.256 SD= .7842								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.79, 3.28, 2.88, 3.23, and 3.10 with corresponding standard deviations of .503, .793, 1.062, .645, and .918 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.256 with the cluster standard deviation of .7842 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that parents' occupation has influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Research Question 3

What is the influence of parents' educational attainment on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State?

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Parents' Educational Attainment on Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	The educational background of my parents significantly shapes my career aspirations.	255	247	0	86	3.14	1.00	Accepted
12	I feel that my career options are influenced by the educational background of my parents.	130	361	9	88	2.91	.910	Accepted
13	My family is supportive in guiding me towards career paths in line with their educational background.	259	214	27	88	3.10	1.07	Accepted
14	My parents have been actively involved in guiding my educational and career decisions.	122	345	35	86	2.86	.912	Accepted
15	I feel that my career options are influenced by the educational status of my parents.	271	200	0	117	3.06	1.12	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation \bar{X}= 3.014 SD= .996								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 3.14, 2.91, 3.10, 2.86, and 3.06 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.000, .910, 1.038, .912, and 1.120 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.014 with the cluster

standard deviation of .996 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that parents' educational attainment has influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Parents' income has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Influence of Parents' Income on Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	187.170	.000	Sig.
SA	161	147.0					
A	277	147.0					
D	80	147.0					
SD	70	147.0					
Total	588						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 187.170$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that parents' income has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State is therefore, not accepted. This implies that parents' income has significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Hypothesis 2

Parents' occupation has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Influence of Parents' Occupation on Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	329.619	.000	Sig.
SA	266	147.0					
A	247	147.0					
D	50	147.0					
SD	25	147.0					
Total	588						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 329.619$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that parents' occupation has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State is therefore, not accepted. This implies that parents' occupation has significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Hypothesis 3

Parents' educational attainment has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Table 7: Chi-square Test of Influence of Parents' Educational Attainment on Career Aspirations of Senior Secondary School Students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	466.735	.000	Sig.
SA	130	147.0					
A	361	147.0					
D	9	147.0					
SD	88	147.0					
Total	588						

Table 7 revealed that $\chi^2 = 466.735$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that parents' educational attainment has no significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State is therefore, not accepted. This implies that parents' educational attainment has significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions and hypotheses. The three null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding revealed that parents' income has significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State. The findings of the study underscore the pivotal role parental income plays in shaping the career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students. Economic stability within the household often correlates with greater exposure to resources and opportunities, allowing parents to invest in their children's education and career development. This finding is similar to that of Jimoh, Adesanya and Shuaib (2019), who found in a study that parents' educational level, parents' income and parent's occupation influenced career aspirations and choice of students. Higher income levels can provide access to better schools, extracurricular activities, and mentorship programs, which in turn broaden students' horizons and instill confidence in pursuing ambitious career paths. Conversely, students from lower-income households may face barriers such as limited access to educational resources and increased financial pressure, which can constrain their career aspirations. Thus, the influence of parental income on career aspirations highlights the intersection of socioeconomic status and educational outcomes, emphasizing the need for equitable access to resources and support to empower all students to pursue their professional goals regardless of their socioeconomic background.

The second finding revealed that parents' occupation has significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State. The outcomes of the study illuminate the profound impact that parents' occupations wield on the career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students. Parental occupation serves as a potent influence, shaping students' perceptions of various professions and pathways available to them. Children often look to their parents as role models and draw inspiration from their careers, subconsciously molding their own aspirations in alignment with familial vocations or those perceived as prestigious within their social context. In a similar vein, Olanrewaju, Olabisi and Olabisi (2022) also found that parents' socioeconomic status was positively correlated with students' career aspirations. Moreover, parents' occupations can directly influence the level of exposure and understanding their children have regarding different career fields, potentially steering them toward or away from specific professions based on familial experiences and values. Consequently, disparities in parental occupations can exacerbate existing inequalities in career aspirations, underscoring the importance of interventions aimed at broadening students' exposure to diverse career options and providing support to navigate pathways regardless of familial occupational backgrounds. Contrastingly, Obiyo and Eze (2015) found in a study that parental socioeconomic status was not a strong indicator of vocational aspirations of secondary school students.

The third finding revealed that parents' educational attainment has significant influence on career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State. This finding implies that parental educational levels serve as a powerful determinant, shaping students' perceptions of their own potential and the possibilities available to them in the professional realm. This is similar to the finding of Ogbiji (2018), who found that parents' educational levels influenced their children's career aspirations. Children often inherit not only their parents' genes but also their values, attitudes, and aspirations, with higher levels of parental education typically correlating with greater emphasis on academic achievement and career success within the household. Additionally, parents with higher educational attainment tend to possess a deeper understanding of the pathways to various careers and can provide invaluable guidance and support to their children in navigating educational and professional endeavours. Conversely, students from households with lower parental educational attainment may face additional hurdles in accessing information, resources, and support necessary to pursue ambitious career goals. Therefore, addressing disparities in parental educational attainment is crucial for fostering equitable opportunities and empowering all students to aspire to and achieve their career aspirations, irrespective of their familial educational backgrounds.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that parents' socioeconomic status has influence on the career aspirations of Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Township of Benue State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Counsellors should work towards guiding students into career paths that align with their parents' income levels. This could be done by counsellors through realistic career guidance, so that students do not go into careers that are above their parents' financial capacities.
2. Counsellors should, in the process of career guidance understand that parents' occupations influence the choice of careers of their offspring. Therefore, they should seek to get a clear understanding of their career interests, and not those influenced by their parents' occupations.
3. Since parents' educational attainment levels have significant influence on students' career aspirations, it is important that counsellors take into cognizance the levels of education of the parents of their clients. Because, in some cases, income levels and occupations of parents tend to be correlated, therefore, understanding these relationships would be helpful in the process of career guidance.

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